

PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN LINGUISTICS AND THEIR LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE

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ABSTRACT

Phraseologism, phraseological turn or phraseme is a stable phrase characteristic of a certain language, the meaning of which is not determined by the meaning of the individual words that make up its composition. Phraseological units are studied by phraseology. Often the grammatical meaning of phraseological units does not meet the norms of the modern language, but is grammatical archaisms. Examples of such expressions in Russian would be: "stay on your toes", "kick back", "fight back", "play the fool", "point of view", "without a king in your head", "soul to soul", "sewn by whites" threads" and the like.

A phraseological unit is used as a whole that is not subject to further decomposition and usually does not allow rearrangement of its parts within itself. The semantic cohesion of phraseological units can vary over a fairly wide range: from the non-deducibility of the meaning of a phraseological unit from its constituent words in phraseological combinations (idioms) to phraseological combinations with a meaning arising from the meanings that make up the combinations. The transformation of a phrase into a stable phraseological unit is called lexicalization.

Different scientists interpret the concept of a phraseological unit and its properties in different ways, however, the most consistently identified properties of a phraseological unit by various scientists are:

Reproducibility.

Sustainability.

Over-verbalism.

Belonging to the nominative inventory of the language.

The concept of phraseological units (French *unité phraséologique*) as a stable phrase, the meaning of which cannot be derived from the meanings of its constituent words, was first formulated by the Swiss linguist Charles Bally in his work "Précis de stylistique", where he contrasted them with another type of phrase - phraseological groups (French. *séries phraséologiques*) with a variable combination of components. Subsequently, V.V. Vinogradov identified three main categories of phraseological units:

Phraseological adhesions (idioms).

Phraseological unities.

Phraseological combinations.

From the standpoint of historical phraseology B.A. Larin identified three categories of phraseological combinations:

Variable phrases are the most common type of linguistic units. Phraseological combinations also fall into this category (V.V. Vinogradov).

Metaphorical phrases are a rethinking of a variable phrase of the same lexical composition ("bend your back", "wash dirty linen in public"). Idioms (phraseological combinations in the classification of V. V. Vinogradov).

N. M. Shansky supplemented this classification by highlighting the 4th category of phraseological units - phraseological expressions. An alternative classification, in addition to idioms and collocations, includes proverbs, sayings and catchphrases in phraseological units. The most complete classification of phraseological units was proposed by V. P. Zhukov and A. V. Zhukov, identifying five main types:

Historically applied phraseological units endowed with a holistic, unmotivated meaning ("beat the buck"). Applicable phrases that have a holistic, unmotivated meaning in modern language ("to wash the bones"). Applicable phraseological units with a holistic motivated meaning ("lie on your side").

Unapplicable phraseological units, motivated, with a partially holistic meaning, where one of the components is semantically correlated with a monosound word of free use ("under a cheerful hand").

Unapplicable phraseological units, motivated, with a partially holistic meaning, where all components are meaning-forming and correlate with words in their free use ("find a common language"). A phraseological fusion or idiom (from the Greek ἴδιος - "own, characteristic") is a semantically indivisible phrase, the meaning of which is completely indeducible from the sum of the meanings of its constituent components, their semantic independence is completely lost. For example, "Sodom and Gomorrah" - "turmoil, noise." When translating phraseological units literally, a foreigner usually cannot understand their general meaning: in English. to show the white feather - "accuse of cowardice" (literally - "show the white feather", in England a white feather was given to draft dodgers during the war) not a single word hints at the meaning of the entire phrase.

Often, the grammatical forms and meanings of idioms are not determined by the norms and realities of the modern language, that is, such adhesions are lexical and grammatical archaisms. So, for example, the idioms "to kick the bucket" - "to mess around" (in the original meaning - "to split logs into blanks for making household wooden objects") and "carelessly" - "carelessly" reflect the realities of the past that are absent in the present (in the past they was inherently metaphorical). In the conjunctions "from small to large," "without hesitation," archaic grammatical forms are preserved.

Phraseological unity is a stable turnover, in which, however, the signs of semantic separation of components are clearly preserved. As a rule, its overall meaning is motivated by and derived from the meaning of the individual components.

Phraseological unity is characterized by imagery; Each word of such a phrase has its own meaning, but together they acquire a figurative meaning. Typically, phraseological units of this type are tropes with a metaphorical meaning (for example, "gnaw the granite of science," "go with the flow," "cast a fishing rod"). The individual words included in its composition are semantically independent, and the meaning of each of the components is subordinated to the unity of the general figurative meaning of the entire phraseological expression as a whole. However, with a literal translation, a foreigner can guess the meaning of the phrase.

Like idioms, phraseological units are semantically indivisible, their grammatical forms and syntactic structure are strictly defined. Replacing a word as part of a phraseological unity,

including the substitution of a synonym, leads to the destruction of the metaphor (for example, “granite of science”, “basalt of science”) or a change in the expressive meaning: “fall for the bait” and “get caught in the net” are phraseological synonyms, but express different shades of expression.

However, unlike idioms, unities are subject to the realities of modern language and can allow the insertion of other words between their parts in speech: for example, “bring (yourself, him, someone) to a white heat,” “pour water into the mill (of something) either or someone)” and “to pour water into (one’s own, someone else’s, etc.) mill.”

Examples: “come to a dead end”, “beat the key”, “hold a stone in your bosom”, “lead by the nose”; English to know the way the cat is jumping - “to know where the wind is blowing” (literally - “to know where the cat will jump”).

A phraseological combination is a stable phrase that includes words with both a free meaning and phraseologically related, non-free (used only in this combination). Phraseological combinations are stable phrases, but their holistic meaning follows from the meanings of the individual words that make them up.

Unlike phraseological adhesions and unities, combinations are semantically divisible - their composition allows limited synonymous substitution (replacement of individual words), while one of the members of the phraseological combination turns out to be constant, while the others are variable: for example, in the phrases “burn with love, hatred, shame, impatience” the word “burn” is a constant member with a phraseologically related meaning.

A limited range of words can be used as variable members of a combination, determined by semantic relations within the language system: for example, the phraseological combination “burn with passion” is a hyponym in relation to combinations like “burn with ...”, while by varying the variable part it is possible to form synonymous rows of “burn with shame, disgrace, disgrace”, “burn with jealousy, thirst for revenge.”

Another example: English. to show one’s teeth - “snap” (literally - “show your teeth”). Semantic independence in this combination is demonstrated by the word “one’s” - “someone’s”. It can be replaced with the words “my”, “your”, “his”, etc.

Phraseological expressions are phraseological units that are stable in their composition and use, which are not only semantically distinct, but also consist entirely of words with a free nominative meaning. Their only feature is reproducibility: they are used as ready-made speech units with a constant lexical composition and certain semantics. Often a phraseological expression is a complete sentence with a statement, edification or conclusion.

Examples of such phraseological expressions are proverbs and aphorisms. If there is no edification in a phraseological expression or there are elements of understatement, then it is a proverb or a catchphrase. Another source of phraseological expressions is professional speech. The category of phraseological expressions also includes speech cliches - stable formulas such as “all the best”, “see you again”, etc.

Many linguists do not classify phraseological expressions as phraseological units, since they lack the basic features of phraseological units.

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